

SLR of Emotional Intelligence Models and Future Research Agenda

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Abstracts: This article is written with an aim to review the literature from the start of the concept and the most famous model developed in the history of this subject. Three models presented in this paper and a strategic literature review is done. The readers of these papers can understand the full concept and related details in one document. For academicians, this paper can be helpful in making student understand the full details of the models that can be used for understanding and implications. For authors and researchers, this article contribute by putting all related literature at one place and can consult this paper for itemized tools in the context of calculation of the concept.

Keywords: Emotions, Emotional Intelligence, Personal Intelligence, Interpersonal relationship.

I. Emotional Intelligence

Emotional literacy, Emotional Intelligence, Personal Intelligence, Social Intelligence, and Interpersonal Intelligence have all been used to illustrate this human IQ. Unintelligible level (Dulewicz & Higgs, 2012). The concept of emotional quotient (EQ) was first proposed by Daniel Goleman. In his book *Emotional Quotient*, he puts forward the concept of "emotional intelligence." Later, the concept was promoted in the magazine "Time" in the United States, and wrote: Whether life is successful, in the true sense, determining whether a person is successful, not IQ, but the level of emotional intelligence, since then, emotional intelligence the concept is very popular. At first, this concept caused a lot of controversy in the academic world. Later, the essence of this concept developed a more pragmatic side, which has gradually become accepted. When the concept of emotional quotient (EQ) is proposed, the controversies that arise include:

People who use emotional intelligence (EI) are basically inclined to think that emotions cannot be measured by quotient. People who use emotional intelligence (EIQ) compare the wisdom of knowing emotions with the concept of IQ (IQ), so they become "emotional intelligence." We now call EQ, which refers to EIQ. When we identify EQ In fact, after the abbreviation of EIQ, the essence of EQ has actually changed, from a simple emotional quotient to an emotional intelligence quotient. That is to say, it becomes not measuring your emotional index (quotient). It is in measuring your understanding of emotions and the ability to control emotions and self-emotion management. The degree of understanding and self-control of emotions can be measured. Therefore, it is less controversial to measure the intelligence quotient of emotions. In order to simplify these concepts, this thesis includes Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Emotional Intelligence Quotient (EIQ) for emotional intelligence (EIQ). And emotional intelligence (EIQ) and emotional intelligence (Emotional Intelligence, EI) are used interchangeably unless otherwise noted.

Daniel Goleman's concept of emotional quotient is precisely because he believes that only 20% of life's achievements are attributed to intelligence, and 80% are affected by other factors; but these factors have not been systematically summarized and analyzed. Later, Daniel Goleman mentioned in his book *"Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ"* that the level of emotional intelligence is the key to determining personal career success and happiness. He also further put forward: "In the past, people in the education and training process often only focused on training and improving people's IQ, but did not pay due attention to emotional intelligence. In fact, what is more important for a leader is his Emotional intelligence is not his IQ."

He analyzes these other factors, mainly emotional intelligence, and the emotional intelligence proposed by Daniel Goleman, including; how to motivate yourself to become more and more frustrated?, how to restrain the impulse delay

satisfaction?, How to adjust emotions and avoid thinking ability due to excessive frustration? and how to put yourself in the shoes of the people and always hope for the future?

Finally, combining Daniel Goleman and Salovey's view, emotional intelligence should be a series of capabilities from the inside out as; know your own emotions, Those who do not understand their true feelings (will become slaves to feelings), Proper management of emotions (People who are comfortable with emotions can quickly get out of the low tide), Self-encouragement (People who can motivate themselves and keep enthusiasm are more efficient), Cognition of other people's emotions (empathy, can put themselves in the shoes of others), Management of interpersonal relationships (interpersonal relationship is the art, leadership, and interpersonal harmony that manages the emotions of others). In summary, from 1990, Mayer and Salovey defined emotional intelligence as a social intelligence. Afterwards, the definition of emotional intelligence has been continuously improved. The representative definition in Chinese foreign studies is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Definition of Emotional Intelligence

Representative figure	Definition
Mayer and Salovey (1990)	The ability to monitor one's and others' emotions, the ability to distinguish emotions, and the ability to use them to guide their thinking and actions
Goleman (1995)	The ability to suppress mood swings, analyze other people's emotions, and handle interpersonal relationships
Bar on (1997)	The comprehensive non-cognitive ability and skills of people to properly cope with external environmental stress
Xu Xiaoyan, Zhang Jinfu (2002)	Non-cognitive mental ability that influences success in learning, life, and work
Xu Yuanli (2004)	The ability to process and process emotional information and solve emotional problems
Lu Jiasheng (2005)	A person's ability to manipulate emotions

II. Background

At the earliest American scholars Mayer and Salovey first defined Emotional Intelligence and proposed a theoretical model of three dimensional emotional intelligence. Subsequently, a group of scholars such as Goleman and Bar-on conducted in-depth research on emotional intelligence. The theory of emotional intelligence gradually matured, and empirical research became more and more extensive, gradually expanding from the field of psychology to management. In the field of field of education, Zhao Tongsen, Wang Xiaotong, Xu Xiaoyan, Zhang Jinfu and others have combined the Chinese background to conduct research on emotional intelligence. (Pinar, W., & Hua, Z., 2016) The current empirical research on emotional intelligence has become the main trend. In the field of management, the research focuses on the relationship between employee intelligence and managerial intelligence and job performance, job satisfaction, job burnout, etc.

According to the Chinese Journal Full-text Database (CNKI) on December 18, 2018, there are about 1,516 articles on emotional intelligence and emotional ability, including doctoral, master's, and academic papers. From the early 1990s to 2017, there are different papers published. It can be seen that the discussion and research on emotional intelligence, both in depth and breadth, have attracted some scholars in China. There are 51 articles of literature, emotional intelligence and job burnout in the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance, while there are two articles on emotional intelligence, job burnout and job performance.

Pinar, W., & Hua, Z., (2016) Meta-analysis of the relationship between intelligence and work-related variables by taking the Chinese sample as an example, the method of research is to use second-hand data for research and analysis, as there is no direct data available for analysis. To test the hypothesis of this study, we used SmartPLS software to run PLS-SEM. PLS-SEM has become a widespread technique in management and marketing literature and has been utilized by several previous studies such as (Farrukh, Ting, et al., 2018; Farrukh et al., 2019; Farrukh, Alzubi, et al., 2018; Farrukh, Lee, & Shahzad, 2019; Farrukh, Meng, Sajid, & Shahzad, 2020). Sun, Liu, & Yu, (2019) explained as "The relationship between local psychological capital and professional well-being". This study used 1566 lecturers as a research sample to analyze psychological capital. The relationship between professional well being, and psychological capital contains emotional intelligence. Vocational happiness includes burnout, turnover intention and job performance. Individual performance yields organizational performance when collectively and holistically viewed (Shahzad & Bhatti, 2008; Shahzad, I. A., Raju, V., et al., 2018; Shahzad, Farrukh, Yasmin, 2020). However, because it contains too many variables, it could not directly assess the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance. For example, psychological capital includes eight elements as; Hope, optimism, tenacity, confidence, altruism, gratitude, emotional ability, self-improvement, so the relationship between variables could not be established as directly extended to the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance.

According to a study by Towers Watson's 2018 Global Workforce, 51% of Chinese employees felt the need of shifting to other organizations to advance their career and job levels. Most of the previous research studies are quantitative in nature and focused on performance related issues (Chew & Wong, 2008), have overlooked education staff issues (do Amaral & Christie., 2019). More specifically, very rare studies are actually focused on the front employees and managers in education industry (Radzi et al., 2009). Limited research has been conducted on the talented employees especially teaching level performance (Jaffari et al., 2011).

The relationship between HR practices and talented employees' performance still needs consideration and has remained unclear (Bryant & Allen, 2013). Furthermore, despite of importance of the topic, it has not yet explored which HR practices are more significantly related to employees' performance (Abii et al., 2013). Moreover, Kinnie, Purcell and Hutchinson (2005) illustrated that organizations use different ways to manage clerical staff, front line, staff and high professionals. Furthermore, they argued that different group level has different skills, motivation and expectation at workplace. According to Purcell and Hutchinson (2007) organizations have to be more concerned and careful while managing talented employees, who are the front and middle line positions because they are directly involved in achievements. Therefore, there is a need to understand the causes and the processes which make middle level employees to perform (Li, Wang, & Gu, 2019).

Based on the above situation and the author's work experience in universities, 10 universities in Shanxi Province were selected as samples to explore the emotional intelligence, exhaustion, job burnout, empowerment enhancement, turnover intention, of university lecturers as a breakthrough point, and self-efficacy as mediating variables to analyze the impact on the performance of University lecturers. Some ideas on improving the emotional intelligence quotient of university lecturers are helpful to improve the efficiency and efficiency of both individual lecturers and Chinese universities, and to enhance the competitiveness of the organization.

III. Strategic Literature Review

Emotional Intelligence

Goleman (2012) defines in his book Emotional Quotient: Emotion refers to feelings and their unique state of mind, physiology and psychology, and related behavioral tendencies. Bandurau (2014) believes that positive emotions can express one's self-confidence and predict future success. Leaders with stable moods and good interpersonal relationships often perform more successfully than those with high IQs. De Beauport and Diaz (2013) argue that emotional intelligence is the intelligence that promotes proper feelings and desires, including: Affection Intelligence, Mood Intelligence, and Motivational Intelligence.

Shapiro (2014) Emotional intelligence is considered to include emotional management, moral development, emotional thinking, problem solving, social skills, self-motivation, and emotional expression. Organizational structure, work characteristics are significant when overall human resources development is the concern (Shahzad, Bhatti & Khalid, 2007; Shahzad et al., 2018). Goleman (2015) further points out that emotion are a mental state with a strong sensory component. In terms of reason and sensibility, in the decision-making process, the proportion of emotional considerations is not lower than rationality, and even when it is. Generally speaking, the influence of sensibility on

psychology is high. When the situation is more critical, the rational thinking is unable to play its role. That is to say, when the passionate emotion destroys this equilibrium, the result is usually perceptual overwhelming rationality and from the personal experience, the memory of emotions is often very profound, such as, falling out of love, respecting the image of the teacher, etc. Therefore, the impact of emotion on people is profound and unexpected.

According to Taiwanese scholars Cai Xiuling and Yang Zhixin (2016), emotions are caused by stimuli. When emotions occur, they will respond at four levels: physical, psychological, cognitive, and behavioral, and the response will vary from person to person. The importance of emotions concerns everyone, because they have the functions of survival, interpersonal communication and motivation. Emotional transmission of information, understanding the stimulus that triggers emotions will enable individuals to better understand the truth and have more control. Secondly, emotion is also a system of adjustment. Repression, indulgence or overreaction can cause problems. Therefore, learning and understanding of emotions is one of the important conditions for promoting mental health. The definition of emotions consists of four levels;

IV. Theories and Representative Models of Emotional Intelligence

1. Ability Model of Emotional Intelligence Mayer and Salovey

Emotional Intelligence, first proposed by Yale University's Salovey & New Mohan University Mayer, gradually became accustomed to the emotional quotient EQ (Emotional Quotient). Mayer, Dipaolo & Salovey believes that emotional intelligence is a ability to detect the feelings and emotions of oneself and others, and to distinguish between emotions, and then to deal with emotions and use emotional messages to guide individuals' thinking and action.

The concept, connotation and scope of emotional intelligence are as; Emotional assessment and expression: Emotional assessment and expression include emotional perception and expression of oneself and others. Cognizing your own emotions: Verbal speaks about expression or nonverbal physical movements and body language, and correctly and expediently perceives your inner actual emotional feelings. Cognizing the emotions of others: Through non-verbal perception and empathy, to understand the true feelings of others, to put yourself in the shoes of others and to observe the emotional feelings of others. Emotional adjustment: Emotional adjustment is an important component of emotional intelligence, including the ability to adjust one's own emotions and adjust others' emotions. Adjust your emotions: Individuals can use past experience to adjust and improve negative emotions and pressures to maintain a happy mood and positive emotions.

Dealing with the emotions of others: not only should we adjust our emotions appropriately, but also provide timely appease and encouragement, adjust the emotional reactions of others, and establish good interpersonal relationships. The use of emotions: using incentives to transform the emotions of oneself and others, and to turn negative into positive emotions. Flexible plan: Use the change of emotions to help us think about future plans, make more choices, and make the best preparations. Creating thinking: Different emotional feelings will affect the solution of the problem. Optimistic emotions contribute to creative and inductive work, while pessimistic emotions sometimes contribute to deductive thinking. Transfer of attention: Emotion can help to measure the priority of things, moderately shift attention to more important stimuli to reduce the occurrence of errors and Stimulating the engine: Positive and constructive emotions can be used to stimulate the engine, build self-confidence, interpersonal relationships, and face the challenges of adversity, so as to improve job performance. Model of Salovey & Mayer's emotional intelligence is given in the figure 1.

As shown in figure 2.1. Emotional intelligence includes three dimensions: emotional assessment and expression, emotional regulation and emotional use. The first two dimensions involve both self and others. After several years of controversy and thinking, in 1997, Meyer and Solovy revised the above theoretical model, expanded the original three dimensionality into four dimensions, and proposed the ability of emotion to promote thinking, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Meyer and Solovy's four dimensional emotional intelligence theoretical model

1	Perception, assessment, expression of dimensional emotion	Content recognition emotions, ability to accurately express emotions
2	Emotional thinking	Ability to change different emotional states by adjusting attention
3	Understand, analyze emotions and apply emotional knowledge	Identify the meaning of emotional expression and the ability to use emotions flexibly
4	Reflective emotional regulation that promotes emotional and intellectual development	The ability to reflect on one's and others' emotions

Later, in order to compare with the theoretical model of emotional intelligence of Gorman and others, in May Meyer and Sorovy improved the four-dimensional model of 1997, which is reduced to: the first dimension is emotional perception that, perceives oneself, others. The second dimension is the use of emotions, that is, emotions promote thinking in a constructive way, generating emotions for judgment and memory: the third dimension is emotional understanding, that is, understanding the relationship between complex emotions and emotional transformation; the fourth dimension is Emotional management, that is, reflective regulation of emotions, promotes the development of emotions and intelligence.

According to the above model, Salovey & Mayer's emotional IQ thinking includes the ability to distinguish one's and others' emotions (including speech, non-verbal, empathy), regulate oneself, even regulate others' emotions, use their emotions, and influence their thinking. And action, and using emotional information to guide thinking includes flexible planning, creative thinking, motivation, and attention shift. The definition of emotional intelligence as suggested by Mayer, Salovey and their recent colleague David Caruso runs as under "The ability to process emotional information, particularly as it involves the Perception,Assimilation, Understanding and Management of emotions".

2. Goleman's Model of emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman (1995) Emotional Intelligence "Is actually a constellation of abilities, skills and dispositions which, when taken together, can predict a person's likelihood of future success in a number of areas, including one's ultimate niche in society".

Goleman proposes an emotional ability matrix to diagnose emotional intelligence, which includes the relationship between the five emotional intelligences and twenty-five emotional abilities, as shown in the following table. Everyone has their own strengths and weaknesses, and Goleman believes that only by taking advantage of one of the six competencies can lead to excellence in performance through a diverse approach. It spans five areas of emotional intelligence, including self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. These abilities have five characteristics and connections; Independent: Each competency has its own unique contribution to performance, Dependent: Each ability depends more or less on its ability and has strong dependence on each other, Stepped: Each emotional intelligence is based on another emotional intelligence, arranged in a stepped manner, Necessary but not sufficient conditions: When there is a basic emotional intelligence, it is not guaranteed to develop or demonstrate relevant abilities and Derived: This list of capabilities can be applied to almost all work, but different job natures will have different competency requirements.

Gorman's theoretical model of emotional intelligence, as shown in Figure 2.2. Emotional intelligence includes five factors: self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, and social skills. Details are grouped in table 3.

Table 3

Emotional Capability Architecture

Self-Awareness: Know your inner state, preferences, resources, and intuition

1. Emotional awareness: recognize your emotions and their influence

2 Correct self-assessment: understand your strengths and limitations

3. Self-confidence: affirming self-worth and ability

Self-Regulation - handles its own internal state, impulses and resources

4. Self-control: deal with your own emotions and impulses

5. Trustworthy: Maintaining honest and complete value standards

6. Conscience: Responsible for your performance

7. Resilience: the ability to handle change

8. Innovation: the heart and ability to accept new ideas, new knowledge

Motivation: An emotional trend that leads or encourages a goal.

9. Achievement drive: strive to improve or achieve excellence standards

10. Borrowing: Participating in group or organizational goals

11. Initiative: Prepare to wait for an opportunity

12. Liang Guan: ignoring obstacles, frustrations, persistence in pursuing goals

Empathy: Perceive the emotions, needs, and concerns of others

13. Know others: You can feel the emotions and opinions of people, and take care of things that others care about.

14. Service Orientation: anticipate, recognize and meet the needs of customers 15. Help others develop: feel the development needs of others and support their ability

16. Make good use of diversity: seek and recreate new opportunities by the disparity of group members

17. Political Confidence: Explain the emotional darkness and power relations of a group

Social Skill: The maturity that triggers an appropriate response

18. Influence: Play an effective art of dressing

19. Communication: Deliver clear, convincing messages

20. Team Township: Inspiring and guiding groups and people

21. Change Catalysis: Initiate or Process Changes

22. Handling conflicts: negotiating and resolving disputes

23. Establish a quick knot: cultivate a relationship with a pot

24. Division of labor and cooperation: working with others to achieve common goals

25. Team Capabilities: Creating the synergy of groups in pursuing common goals

"Emotional awareness" is the ability to feel and distinguish different emotions. "Emotional use" is the process of using emotions to guide thinking. "Emotional understanding" is the process of establishing personal knowledge about emotional causes and emotional changes. "Emotional management" It is an emotional response that is efficient and translates into a mindset of appropriate decision making. These four theoretical facets characterize emotional responses and translate them into mental models of appropriate decision making. These four theoretical facets represent the order relationship of emotional IQ operations.

They can be sensitive to emotions before they can apply this sensory emotions to emotional communication and cognitive operation systems, and then through emotional assembly and relationship changes. Comprehend emotional intelligence, and finally use the individual's understanding of emotional knowledge to self-reflect and adjust emotions, and then achieve the effects and abilities of emotional management.

In recent years, Emotional Intelligence has been widely recognized by all walks of life. Emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize and manage one's emotions. It also believes that emotional intelligence has the characteristics of establishing relationships and quality of relationships. The research by Steven, Anthony, & Uanessa (2012) confirms that the cooperative team with higher emotional intelligence has better organizational performance, because in the process of teamwork, the higher the emotional intelligence, the more harmonious the communication, the work partners can be relaxed and happy. In the work environment, connect to the organizational goals. Therefore, for modern enterprise organizations, emotional intelligence has become a key factor in business success. Recent research indicates that Professor Roger Weissberg's research (Case Western Reserve University, 2015).

Since Salovey and Mayer have studied the emotional intelligence theory of interpersonal interaction and personal self-sufficiency, there have been researches and discussions on related issues. Mayer and Salovey believe that emotional intelligence leads people to think more closely and use creativity to solve emotional problems. Goleman (1995)6 broadly defines the concept of emotional intelligence, including the range of emotional characteristics of Shanjie, further elucidating emotional intelligence, applying emotional intelligence to job orientation, and proposing the influence of workers' emotional intelligence on job performance. Key points: (1) Personal ability: How do we manage ourselves (2) Social ability: How do we manage the relationship between people, and propose self-awareness, self-emotion management, self-motivation, empathy, interpersonal relationship as emotions The facet of IQ, and its continuous extension and empirical research on the company, more detailed and used by late researchers

3. Reuven Bar-On Model of emotional Intelligence

Bar On, (2002) defines emotional intelligence as "an array of interrelated emotional and social competencies, skills and facilitators that determine how well we understand and express ourselves, understand others and relate with them and cope with daily demands, challenges and pressures" (Bar-On 1997).

Scholar Bar-On proposed a model of emotional intelligence, which is different from previous scholars' understanding of emotional intelligence. He defined emotional intelligence as "emotional IQ is the sum of emotional ability that affects individuals' ability to cope with environmental needs and stress. A series of non-cognitive abilities and skills" (He Xiaolei 2014; Mu Niankui et al. 2013). Bar-On's emotional intelligence includes five elements, including self-awareness, interpersonal relationships, resilience, stress management, and integrated emotions. The biggest difference between Bar-On's emotional IQ model and previous scholars is the more practical and concerned about the applicability of emotional intelligence.

Table 4

Barron's emotional intelligence theory model

Dimension	content
1 Introspective ability	Self-acceptance; self-realization; emotional self-perception; independence
2 Adaptability	Flexibility; problem solving; reality test
3 communication ability	Empathy; social responsibility; interpersonal relationship
4 Stress management	Control impulse
5 General emotional state	Optimism

In 1997, Barry proposed the emotional intelligence model mainly consists of five factors, as shown in Table 2.4. He believes that individuals with high emotional intelligence are characterized by strong ability, success and emotional health.

China's theoretical research on emotional intelligence is gradually unfolding. Xu Yuanli (2004) constructed a three-dimensional composite structure model of emotional intelligence, which believes that emotional intelligence includes objects, operations and content, in which objects refer to the subject of emotional intelligence research, and operations refer to emotions. The process and method of mental activity in intellectual research, the content refers to emotional or emotional information of different meanings. Zhang

Huihua (2008) proposed a theoretical model of managerial emotional intelligence, which includes four dimensions: relationship processing, work intelligence, interpersonal sensitivity, and emotion regulation. These four dimensions can be further divided into two areas, namely, work area and self-domain. Their theoretical models of emotional intelligence have also been proved by empirical research.

In modern academic circles, Salovey and Mayer were defined as "capacity emotional intelligence models" (Yue Hong, Zhang Jian 2016; Mu Niankui et al. 2013), which is mainly academic, with emphasis on defining what is emotional intelligence. Goleman and Bar-On are defined as mixed emotional intelligence model (Yue Hong, Zhang Jian 2016; Zhang Xiang 2011; Wang Shuhong 2012; Zhang Huihua 2012; Mu Niankui et al 2013; Yao Jihai, Guan Haijuan 2016), that is practice is the main focus, how the emotion affects interpersonal relationships and how to drive emotional intelligence, so that individuals can perform at their best. So in recent years, many researchers have redefined emotional intelligence. According to The Chartered Management Institute, "emotional intelligence" is seen as "perceived, understood, integrated personal abilities and manages the emotional and emotional abilities of oneself and others, and based on these.

The way the action is taken." Palmer and Stough (2013) also suggested that when "emotional IQ" is used in the work environment, it should include practical actions and include a professional and effective approach. The American Training and Development Association The American Society for Training and Development (ASTD) insists that constructive interactions at work are more conducive to the development of the work environment. A good working environment can make it easier for senior management to make decisions, so that other companies have good Job performance.

Therefore, the views and definitions of modern emotional intelligence are more inclined to practice and application and the mixed emotional intelligence model with Goleman and Bar-On (Yue Hong, Zhang Jian 2016; Zhang Xiang 2014; Wang Shuhong 2013; Mu Niankui, etc. 2013;) It is practice-oriented, focusing on how emotions affect interpersonal relationships and how to drive emotional intelligence, so that individuals can perform at their best, very consistent.

4. Relationship among emotional intelligence and employee personality factors

Carmeli and Josman (2016) also confirm the positive relationship between university lecturers' emotional intelligence and their task performance and organizational citizenship behavior. Busso (2013) empirical research found that Emotional intelligence can predict its associated performance. The higher the individual's emotional intelligence, the more they adjust their mood, and the more they are willing to provide support and help to others, and the auxiliary work is background performance. Schutte et al. (2017) through empirical research It is found that those who have higher emotional intelligence, in social situations, tend to empathize and stand on the perspective of others. They have higher communication skills. They usually pay more attention to the work team and are also good at creating and maintaining cooperation. And trusting organizational climate

Therefore, we believe that the higher the emotional intelligence of the university lecturer, the higher the enthusiasm he will perform when performing his tasks, the better his job, and the better cooperation with his peers, even for tasks outside the individual scope. Helps to organize goals and they will work hard to achieve them. Tasks outside the scope of the above roles, while not bringing immediate benefits to the organization, can help organizations improve their effectiveness.

Chan, David W. (2012) research shows that there are significant differences in emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and achievement motivation among managers of different management levels, different management positions, and different regions; emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and achievement motivation for high-level, middle-level, and grassroots enterprise managers. Performance has different predictive powers.

There are few empirical studies on the relationship between emotional intelligence and job burnout. Some studies have shown that job burnout can affect the overall emotional response of university lecturers to their work. The concept of emotion is proposed as part of the emotional state and is strongly influenced by the environment (George & Brief, 2013). Job burnout can affect university lecturers' perceptions of their abilities and values. The more support they feel about the work environment, the more optimistic their emotions (Eisnebesrer et al, 2012).

Rhoades and Eisenberger (2015) found through research that some of the personal qualities of university lecturers can affect their job burnout. Emotional intelligence, as a personal trait of a university lecturer, affects the job burnout by changing whether the university lecturer believes that the work environment (such as work environment, personal accomplishment, etc.), and also affects the behavior of the university lecturer and the treatment they enjoy. Job burnout. University lecturers work and live in organizations, are the sum of various organizational relationships, and emotions are the emotions of interpersonal communication.

Their important function is to adjust relationships and behaviors under the guidance of certain goals. As a part of the organization, university lecturers will inevitably experience some fluctuations in their emotions. People with high emotional intelligence have strong ability to perceive, predict and control themselves and their surroundings, and know how to find and use the working environment. People with high emotional intelligence are good at regulating their own and other people's emotional changes, and can coordinate the emergence of interpersonal interactions. Contradictions and conflicts have harmonized interpersonal relationships, laid a good foundation for seeking more work environments, and increased the objective working environment. The difference in emotional intelligence will affect the working environment that university lecturers feel.

People with high emotional intelligence can not only better understand and understand the emotions of other people around them, but also actively use emotional information to take better, positive and constructive behaviors, so it is easier to work with superiors, subordinates and colleagues. Establishing emotions based on personal attraction (Liu Yimei, Wei Xuhua, Chen Xiaohong 2015; Wang Shuhong 2016), reducing job burnout. Bandura (2014) believes that self-efficacy is not only significantly positively correlated with job performance and related behavior, but in fact there is a causal relationship between them. Gist and Mitchell (2015) incorporated the formation and development of self-efficacy into the relationship model between self-efficacy and performance, and considered the feedback mechanism of performance on self-efficacy, and constructed a self-efficacy- performance model. In the model, the outcomes of self-efficacy (such as the level of goals and the persistence of efforts) directly affect the individual's performance level.

It can be seen from the previous discussion that emotional intelligence can explain the variables with more job performance as a whole, but the ways in which it works are diverse. Through different ways, the impact of emotional intelligence on job performance will change accordingly. Understanding the mechanism of emotional intelligence on job

performance is of great value for us to intervene and control the corresponding variables in management practice to improve job performance.

The higher the emotional intelligence of a university lecturer, the better its task performance and associated performance. However, the relationship between them may be affected by a certain intermediary factor. Self-efficacy may be one of the influencing factors. The higher the emotional intelligence of a university lecturer, the stronger his self-efficacy may be, and the greater the confidence he or she will accomplish when completing his or her tasks, the better his job performance will be. In addition, job burnout may also be an influencing factor. Based on the research framework, hypotheses were developed.

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